

Questions rated higher (1):

Starting questions to warm up and to see if they have experience with music recommenders as users:

1. Do you use platforms such as Spotify, Pandora, YouTube,... to listen to music in your role as a private person?
 - 1.1. What's your experience with it? Does it work for you? Are your own songs recommended to you?
2. How do you think that these systems have affected your career (or would have affected them in earlier stages of your career) at the beginning? do you think it would be much different?
3. In the next questions, we want to know your opinion about giving the artist control of the recommendations; which songs will be recommended and to whom it will be recommended. So, if you had free choice and the opportunity to define and influence the recommendations in the systems, what would you do?
 - 3.1. We have prepared something specific: How would you balance which of your songs are recommended? More precisely, which of your music tracks should be recommended more and which less?
 - 3.1.1. And why?
 - 3.2. Would you make differentiations concerning groups of users? For instance, to which group of users some particular songs should be recommended more and to which user groups less or not at all? - what would you do?
 - 3.2.1. And why?
4. In the following questions we want your opinion on how the current system works or how you think that could be improved. Currently, there are groups of artists that are not recommended by the system because of different reasons (e.g., there is not enough information about them available in the system; for instance no ratings yet). Do you think there should be a solution for this not to happen? Do you see any alternatives?
5. Music considered "niche music" is not recommended to many users, should the system nurture diversity (e.g., in terms of genres, styles, artists from all over the world, popular and not-yet-popular) or focus more on recommending what the user is familiar with?
6. If artist X has more music than the artists Y, do you think the system should recommend more music by artist X - or should the recommendation be independent of an artist's repertoire?
7. If new artists (no recordings before on the platform) enter a system with some tracks, potentially an album.

- 7.1. For a given user out of 100 recommendations, how many do you think should be new artists?

8. Now considering that you are an artist who is in the business for several years and you will hopefully come up with new songs over time, what about the balance in recommendations there? Older songs of you versus newer songs of you? And what about your new songs versus songs by other artists?

9. If the system has more users from country X but more artists from country Y, for different reasons, it is possible that artists from X are recommended more or artists from Y are recommended more. What is the behavior that you expect from the system in that case?
 - 9.1. For example, some countries define quotas with minimum of time that radios have to broadcast local music. Do you think such a quota should also apply to automatic recommendations? In that case, artists of the country X would have more chances to be recommended.
 - 9.2. Also in that case, what the users of country X - that has more users - listen to will have a larger impact on what the users of country Y will get recommended. Do you think the recommender system should favor interchanges between countries even if the influence of the one country and the other country could be unbalanced? Or is it better that each country is more isolated in terms of the artists that are recommended?

10. How people listen to music (not only using the systems) is distributed in a particular way, e.g: Currently, overall K-pop is the 7th most listened genre, over R&B and classical music. Such a popularity distribution could also refer to gender, country, or other aspects of the music. Do you think the systems should try to reproduce this behavior from "outside" online platforms, or should try to provoke a change on it? Do you have any idea about how we could define what the 'right' distribution is or could look like?

11. What the systems recommend is related with the revenue that the artists get in the end: Do you think the current model based on number of streams is good or there could be a better model that, for instance, differentiates if a user listens to a song due to a recommendation compared to regular listening?

12. As we have more time we will ask the following questions that are not related: If a user happens to listen to only two or three genres on a platform, do you think the system should recommend only songs of these genres or also recommend other genres than these two or three?

13. In that case that it should, what is the percentage that should recommend 'other' genres? and why?

Questions rated as important (2):

(introduction question):

1. Do you know whether your music is recommended automatically by a system? Maybe you have analytics on that? Or you know from hear-say? Do you have an idea what the impact of this automatic system recommendation has for reaching a bigger audience - for you and in general?
2. What do you think are the most effective channels to increase your audience and make people listen to yo your music more? For example, radio, automatic recommendation on streaming platforms, curated playlists by experts, or playlist by fans, and playing live.
3. Do you get any feedback from the systems about how to reach more users or to make them listen to your music more? In that case, do you take actions based on that information?
4. If the system systematically recommends artists in the group X more than artists in the group Y, do you think this is okay or fair when it reflects users' taste for these groups of artists?
 - 4.1. Now, when these two groups are defined by genre? What do you think?
 - 4.2. And if the two groups are characterised by artist location or "homebase country"? Or characterised by gender? What do you think?
7. (continuation of question 7)
 - 7.2. All kinds of new artists?
 - 7.3. To every user - or only to specific kinds of users? What kind?
8. (continuation of question 8)
 - 8.2. There is also a trade-off with recommending "old, familiar" artists and recommending 'new' artists, what should be the balance between the old and new?